

A semi-mechanistic mathematical model on the interactions between the ovulatory-menstrual cycle and the metabolic and cardiovascular system

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Abstract: The female body, especially the sex hormones and their dynamic interactions with the rest of the body, have been historically understudied. Many disruptions happen precisely in the interactions between two or more subsystems, but systemic interactions that sustain health or pathological states are often overlooked. Consequently, diagnosis and treatments barely take them into consideration. Mathematical modelling allows to study dynamic interactions to better understand the system as a whole. The aim of the current research is to build a semi-mechanistic mathematical model based on physical principles to describe the interactions between the Ovulatory-Menstrual Cycle (OMC), the metabolic and the cardiovascular system. Here, we show preliminary simulation results from coupling Glucose-Insulin (G-I) dynamics to estradiol (E2) and progesterone (P4) levels. The model also includes endometrial tissue growth coupled to the Hypothalamus-Pituitary-Ovary (HPO) axis dynamics throughout the ovulatory cycle. Regarding the cardiovascular system, we model it from a fluid mechanics perspective as a closed loop, to explore the impact of E2 and P4 on blood tension and volumetric flows.

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I. Introduction

The OMC and the sex hormones throughout women's life determine health and life quality beyond menstruating beings. It is key for the society they belong to. The HPO axis, as the center piece of the endocrine system, regulates ovulation and menstruation dynamics. Most of the research regarding women's bodies has focused on the dynamics within this axis, and how to control them from a reproductive perspective.

However, the function of the hormones secreted by the glands along the HPO axis is not only vital for reproductive function, but for the state of health regardless of pregnancy. This is due to a highly complex interactive network of systems [1]. Physiology reaches boundaries to describe such complexity, since the track of causality starts to be unattainable in a living system.

The central nervous system, the metabolic and cardiovascular system, the endocrine and immune system and all the body tissues, interchange signals through the hormones from the HPO axis during every menstrual cycle, mainly E₂ and P₄.

Mathematical modelling allows making simpler abstractions representing reality and dealing with such complexity. This work builds on an initial model where the ovulatory cycle was coupled with the endometrium dynamics [2]. It, therefore, focuses on the interactions between the OMC and the metabolic and the cardiovascular system.

Detached mechanistic mathematical models have been developed to understand isolated dynamics in the systems of interest. For example, there exist mathematical models describing the dynamics of sex hormones and their feedback loops within the HPO axis, along the OMC [3].

Researchers have also developed minimal and mechanism-based models for the G-I dynamics [4][5]. Most of the existing models of the cardiovascular system are focused on the heart electric circuit [6]. The ones describing blood dynamics leave out the kinetic phenomena and introduce boundary conditions with electric analogies [7]. Only one of them considers the cardiovascular system as a closed loop [8].

Previous work on coupling has been focused on the impact of G-I dynamics' on the OMC, showing how disruption in glucose metabolism can impair ovulation in humans [9][10] and cows [11].

To the authors' knowledge, there is no previous work on mechanistic mathematical models describing the impact of the OMC on the metabolism of glucose, nor describing the one on the cardiovascular system.

II. Material and methods

The main steps of the proposed approach as described in [5], are:

- Pre-construction: description of the phenomena, hypothesis and partitioning to define process systems.
- Construction: ordinary differential equations (ODE) systems building, describing mass and energy transformations.
 - Literature review and selection of previously built models describing detached dynamics.
 - Coupling process: modeling the interactions between process systems, via new equations replacing some of the model parameters. This enlarges the level of specification of the models and their extended structure.
- Post-construction: Model validation and analysis.

III. Results and discussion

E₂ acts diversely in the metabolic system with central and peripheral impacts [12]. Its multiple receptors on anorexigenic neurons evidence its action on metabolic homeostasis, centrally [13]. Peripherally, E₂ enhances insulin sensitivity (S_I) in the skeletal muscle, supports the pancreatic secretion of insulin promoting beta cells' function and reduces gluconeogenesis and insulin resistance in the liver [12][13][14]. Regarding P₄, [15] emphasizes the E₂/P₄ ratio impact on S_I (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Right: Interactions HPO axis-peripheral metabolism and cardiovascular function. Left: Cardiovascular system: a closed loop

E₂ and P₄ impact the elasticity of cardiovascular vessels-vasodilation/vasoconstriction-, and endothelial health [16]. E₂ has also an impact on the vagal tone, through estrogen receptors (ERs) on vagal neurons in the CNS [12]. Apparently only P₄ is related to heart rate variability [17]. However, there are contradictory statements. The discussion is going on [18].

Figure 1 shows a representation of the cardiovascular system as a closed loop, and equations (1) and (2) describe the mass balance and a steady state energy balance.

$$\frac{dV}{dt} = \dot{v}_{inl} - \dot{v}_{out} \quad (1)$$

$$P_{out} = \sum \frac{\dot{m}_{inl}}{\dot{m}_{out}} \left(P_{inl} + \rho \frac{v_{inl}^2}{2} \right) - \rho \frac{v_{out}^2}{2} + \frac{W_{RA}}{\dot{m}_{out}} - h_f \quad (2)$$

The heart chambers have an extra dynamic energy balance. The rest of the system is considered as pipeline sections. This work is in progress and preliminary results include pressure waves and blood flows. The next step is to couple E₂ and P₄ effects in blood transport phenomena.

Figure 2 shows the results of E₂ and P₄ effects on blood glucose levels along the OMC. The qualitative E₂ dependence responds to physiological descriptions.

Figure 2. E₂ and P₄ effects on glucose dynamics with [4]

However, the dip in glucose data occurs around ovulation (day 16) [19], while the model predicts a dip around the LH surge – one day earlier. This mismatch accounts to oversimplifications in the minimal model: glucose from meals, liver and kidney's endogenous production are lumped into a constant parameter.

Current work focuses on replace the minimal glucose model with a more detailed one, to capture the signal delays in terms of G-I reactions in tissues and organs. The next step is to perform the coupling methodology with [5] & [11].

IV. Conclusions

The definition of one or more parameters through new mathematical equations, not only extends the model structure, but also can bring a systemic perspective coupling two entire systems.

When coupling, the hypothesis and limitations of the foundational models are transferred to the coupled mathematical model. Therefore, it is vital to work simultaneously on more precise coupling equations, and updates on the selection of the pieces themselves.

AUTHOR'S STATEMENT

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